

Current Issues in the Formation of Spiritually Harmonious Youth

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Abstract: The article examines the need to educate a spiritually and harmoniously developed young generation as part of the renewal and reform of Uzbekistan. The author emphasizes the importance of the spiritual and moral education of young people, as well as updating and reforming the education system.

Keywords: youth, spirituality, reforms in education, patriotism, science and education.

I. INTRODUCTION

Choosing the path of development in the new Uzbekistan, resolutely continuing the process of comprehensive renewal and change in the country, we, simultaneously with the ongoing socio-economic reforms, are seriously approaching the issue of spiritual renewal of society. In both cases, the focus is on the human factor. All our efforts in this direction are aimed at ensuring that the ideas of independence take a strong place in the worldview and way of thinking of our people, in particular, by creating decent living conditions for every citizen.

It is obvious that the criteria for the development of modernity are determined by high mental abilities, scientific potential and, of course, spirituality. The need for a national idea, which ensures the commonality of these criteria and directs it towards a good goal, must always be reflected in the spirit of the people. Consequently, the noble goals of national ideology are embodied in the national psyche of the people, which are a clear expression of its strength and stability.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Today, the effectiveness of the creative work and reforms we carry out is inextricably linked with the effectiveness of educating a harmonious generation, the most active, proactive force of society. Therefore, it is no coincidence that we pay the main attention to spiritual and moral maturity, mental and physical health, and ideological education of young people. The education system, which takes on this responsible task, the updates and deep reforms carried out in it are in the constant focus of our attention at the level of state policy.

In his next Address to the Oliy Majlis, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev also focused on the issue of educating a new generation of strategically thinking, educated and qualified personnel, emphasizing that for all of us, mastering modern knowledge, true enlightenment and high culture should become an enduring necessity of life.

Without any hesitation, we can say that raising a harmonious human personality, caring for the future of a healthy generation is a serious issue related to the future of society and the nation. “Educating the younger generation requires an adequate approach to the real requirements of the country’s development, special accuracy. This definition must express the level of our modern self-awareness as a nation and people, as well as our national thinking, which requires modern development” [1].

In this sense, the level of self-awareness of the people and the nation is determined primarily by the fact that our national ideology, which forms the basis of our national thinking, is manifested in the image of popular beliefs and convictions. For this reason, our sustainable development goals, which are an expression of our noble goals, are also primarily related to the spiritual maturity and ideological convictions of a harmonious generation.

When we look at the history of our ideas, which were the expression of the noble goals of our ancestors, we become witnesses of their inherent commonality in different eras. Since this state manifests itself in the harmony of interests, the harmony of noble goals is determined by the following aspects:

- various tribes, clans and peoples on the way to the independence of the country achieving unity, harmony and cooperation;
- a symbol of devotion to the native land, self-sacrifice in the name of its peace, security and progress, fostering a sense of patriotism;
- raising a new generation that realizes the future prospects, dreams and hopes of the people, the nation;
- the desire for science and enlightenment, achieving heights of spirituality as an important factor determining the prospects and progress of a country, nation, people;
- increasing the economic power of the country, supporting the material well-being of the people.

III. METHODOLOGY & EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

As you can see, the only criterion for all aspirations, goals and objectives are the interests of the country. This goal is manifested in the direct connection of the creative work carried out today in our country, the ongoing large-scale transformations and reforms with the specific human factor. A development strategy that expresses the rational goals of our future perspective is a viable example of these humane ideas.

We always see educated, scientifically talented specialists, a new generation of personnel with high spirituality and enlightenment at the forefront of our national development. Thus, the primary task of higher education is to train competitive specialists who meet modern requirements, to provide industries and industries equipped with the most advanced equipment and technologies, as mature specialists, experts in their field, modern personnel with scientific potential and practical skills.

Here we should note another important factor that ensures the effectiveness of the implementation of the urgent tasks set in the field of the higher education system; it is this factor that determines the content of the reforms we are carrying out to radically update the education system. Let us clarify that when it comes to training mature specialists, one should first of all keep in mind the personality of a specialist who meets the most advanced requirements and is able to withstand the intellectual, scientific and technical, spiritual, moral and ideological upheavals of the time. However, such compatibility and preparation cannot be measured by specific requirements alone. Thus, if we define a specialist-personnel limited by his professional training, skills and abilities, then we will not be able to go beyond the definition of a “poor specialist” who evaluates the situation solely from his own professional interests, planning to benefit from it twice as much more in exchange for their knowledge and abilities, which will be

spent on society. At the same time, we set ourselves the goal of educating a specialist who, aware of the social significance of his specialty, will constantly improve his professional skills, mobilize him to achieve the goals of national uplift in the interests of society, and cultivate a sense of pride and pride, a sense of material and spiritual satisfaction. Thus, despite the fact that higher education is an educational institution that provides personnel only for specialists with higher education, this system gives our youth knowledge, a profession, and a specialty, forming in them a culture of free thinking and an independent worldview, defining its spiritual and moral appearance and directing it towards social activity, creativity and initiative, ensuring high morale. we should consider it as an educational environment that develops qualified personnel into the image of a perfect person.

True, the task of higher education, the development of related fields and branches of science, raising it to the level of world standards, first of all, is unconditional, to prepare specialists with scientific potential, capable of combining deep knowledge in their field in harmony with theoretical knowledge and practical skills, is irrefutable truth. It should also be noted that any progress and product of scientific activity must undoubtedly serve the common cause - national progress, along with the acceleration of social progress based on the harmony of national and universal values. Only then will we see in the image of the specialists we have trained an expression of the qualities of high spirituality, professional culture, enlightenment and national education.

Touching upon the issue of spirituality of specialist personnel, it should be noted that education in each specialty should include a combination of individual and social qualities; this harmony becomes a factor in demonstrating the level of knowledge and professional etiquette of a specialist. This factor determines the spiritual and moral criteria of the level and professional culture of a specialist.

IV. RESULTS

They are as follows:

- take an active position in accordance with specific goals and plans, feeling the responsibility of their profession in the chosen direction;
- achieving respect and attention through demonstrating one's abilities, knowledge and professional skills, as well as the level of compliance with one's place and position;
- determination for team cohesion and cooperation with the courage to influence others by expressing their thoughts, ideas and plans in Clear, fluent speech;
- achieving harmony of political consciousness and legal culture as a carrier of modern knowledge;
- set an example for others through self-control within certain moral standards as a representative of a separate social group;
- be able to convince, organize and monitor every decision made by others;
- manifestation of social activity and initiative, responsibility, responsibility, duty and responsibility.

All of these criteria dictate the priority of the subject's personal qualities. So, speaking about the personal qualities and spirituality of a specialist with a higher education, we should pay attention to another important factor that determines the quality of education. The more it is necessary to strengthen the material and technical base of higher education while increasing the level of knowledge, qualifications and skills of a specialist, the more it is necessary to adapt and strengthen the spiritual and educational base of the system to the requirements of the time. The more we attach importance to advanced foreign experience in the field of education, the more we must strengthen the meaning and significance of our national values in the spiritual and educational direction.

Based on the content of our topic, without overestimating any particular discipline or area of education, it is worth noting that in the educational direction, the social sciences set their goals and objectives, aimed at developing a worldview, a culture of thinking, social activity and the life position of youth students. educates [2]. As noted in the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures for the further development of the higher education system": "In order to increase the spiritual and moral content of higher education, deeply penetrate into students the spirit of commitment to the ideas of independence, the national tradition of high spirituality and humanity, strengthening their immunity and critical thinking towards alien ideas and ideologies, large-scale educational activities are carried out. and educational work "[3]. The functional tasks of the comprehensive development of higher education and increasing the efficiency of teaching social studies are identified.

Based on the requirements of this resolution, the ongoing reforms in the higher education system are aimed, first of all, at achieving the effectiveness of the quality of education, creative use and introduction of the most advanced and modern foreign practices into our national education system. Strengthening the material and technical base of the system, providing mature specialists, scientific and pedagogical personnel, increasing scientific potential and creating integration "education-science-production" through the consistent establishment of development work, coordination with regional economic potential are the ultimate goal of the work being carried out in this direction.

An important factor for positive changes in the industry is the creation of sufficient opportunities to strengthen, increase the status and responsibility of disciplines directly related to increasing the spiritual and moral content of higher education, in particular the social sciences, to ensure the effectiveness and practical participation of these disciplines in the education of a harmoniously developed generation capable with their knowledge and ideological convictions to resist the intensity of world events.

Indeed, when teaching social studies, it is necessary to especially emphasize the specifics arising from their functional responsibilities. After all, social sciences, along with the formation of a culture of thinking among schoolchildren, guide them to express their attitude to changes and events occurring in external reality, make personal decisions and draw conclusions. The importance of the issue lies in the fact that when forming a general worldview about reality among young people, it is first of all necessary to correctly interpret the essence of this reality, to clarify the opinion of young people on the basis of specific data about current events, their directions, driving forces and goals. Such a responsible task falls on the philosophical sciences, which have a more ideological status.

Therefore, an in-depth study of social sciences makes it possible to comprehend the world through a culture of thinking, logically observe its essence and thereby form a holistic vision. In this sense, our ideas and conclusions about the external world, about the existence that surrounds us, can be considered as a product of our mental abilities and as a result of systemic influence, that is, the continuity and purposefulness of the educational process. Therefore, when teaching these subjects at higher levels of the education system, we should avoid confusion, similarity or duplication by focusing on uniqueness in science curricula, educational literature and educational technology.

When teaching social studies, we must first of all pay serious attention to the humanistic nature of science. Therefore, it is necessary to ensure the priority of humanism, patriotism, education, hard work, tolerance and dedication in the ideas that we instill in the minds and hearts of our youth. Based on this goal, in order to further deepen the knowledge of our young people in the social sciences, increase their mental maturity, level of knowledge and level of thinking, it is necessary to develop mental education.; implementation of moral education associated with the formation of spiritual, moral, human qualities; legal and political education aimed at developing political and legal awareness, increasing legal culture through the provision of legal and political

knowledge; aesthetic education, aimed at developing aesthetic consciousness and creativity skills, should become the main direction of our educational work.

It is at this moment that the ideological and educational status of the social sciences becomes obvious as one of the most important and basic functional tasks. The educational task of social sciences is to develop in the minds of young people the ability to resist various harmful and alien ideas at the same time as defining an unconditional, independent worldview, freedom of thought and common sense. In a word, the teaching of these disciplines fully meets the requirements for the formation of ideological immunity among young people. This task of the social sciences stands out clearly due to its relevance in today's processes of globalization. "Especially in today's extremely complex and disturbing world, where every day more and more sources, types and forms of dangers and threats penetrate our lives both from within and from without, in such harsh times, without a sense of awareness, a person, society and people lose sensitivity, unconsciously giving his will into the hands of evil forces, unconsciously turning into a complex system of life and development, on his way he reaches a dead end and is distracted from his main goals" [4].

Let us note that in each of his speeches, the president connects the progress of science with socio-economic growth, primarily with the rise of spirituality and enlightenment, with the strength of ideological convictions. This means that fundamental changes and technological development processes carried out in Uzbekistan must be carried out on the basis of a national program based on a comprehensively developed strong national idea.

Another fact that does not require proof is that we have set clear goals and objectives for national upliftment. "To do this, first of all, we need to educate a new generation of people who will become proactive reformers, strategically thinking, educated and qualified. To increase the level of knowledge, the level of not only young people, but also our entire society, first of all, science-enlightenment, high spirituality" [5].

V. CONCLUSIONS

Turning to the wisdom of our wise people, it is clear that it is impossible to imagine that science teaches, teaches on the path from spirituality and enlightenment, culture and, of course, education. Only through the unity of education and upbringing do we enrich the worldview of our youth, deepen their thoughts, clarify their goals and aspirations, encourage them to look at the world in a new way, through the eyes of science and enlightenment.

Based on the content of our field, we drew attention to the importance of social sciences in the training of specialists with higher education. In addition to the above, we can say that if education in special disciplines is aimed at training highly qualified personnel, then the main goal of education in social sciences is to educate a spiritually mature, harmonious generation, possessing common sense and thinking, looking at the surrounding reality through the eyes of truth and justice, capable direct their knowledge and strength towards the development of society towards national uplift.

VI. REFERENCES

1. M.Munavvarova. Milliy g'oyaning ma'naviy ildizlari. T., "Ma'naviyat" 2011. 25-bet
2. Raxmonov A., Safarov A . O'zbekistonning milliy tiklanishdan yuksalish sari rivojlanish bosqichlari. T., "O'zbekiston faylasuflari milliy jamiyati" nashriyoti. 2020. 121 bet
3. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2017 yil 20 apreldagi - Oliy ta'lim tizimini yanada rivojlantirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risidagi PQ -2909- sonli Qarori.// lex.uz
4. Abdurahmonov Qalandar. O'zbekistonda inson omili va manfaatlari – eng oliy qadriyat. T., G'ofur G'ulom nomidagi nashriyot matbaa ijodiy uyi. Toshkent – 2017. 219 bet
5. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining Oliy Majlisga Murojaatnomasi. // Xalq so'zi gazetasi, 2018 yil 23 dekabr.

6. Tursunovich, Q. A. (2022). Hozirgi davrda dunyoning ekologik manzarasi: tabiatni muhofaza qilish global muammo sifatida. *Uzbek scholar journal*, 5, 83-86.
7. Tursunovich, K. A. (2022). Globalization of ecological problems and problems of state sovereignty. *Uzbek Scholar Journal*, 5, 80-82.
8. Tursunovich, Q. A. (2023). Ekologik xavfsizlik masalasi va globallashuv jarayonlari. *Barqarorlik va yetakchi tadqiqotlar onlayn ilmiy jurnali*, 3(3), 255-258.
9. Kubayeva S. Language Games in cognitive processes: constructive-semantic approach //Conferencea. – 2023. – C. 156-159.
10. Yuldasheva D. Legal protection of women is the basis for the development of uzbek society //Gospodarka i Innowacje. – 2022. – T. 24. – C. 1011-1014.
11. Mardonov R. The role of social and humanitarian disciplines in the professional development of students //Conferencea. – 2021. – C. 17-21.
12. Усмонов Ф. Н. Эпистемологическая эволюция рационализма //Наука и современность. – 2012. – №. 19-1. – С. 194-198.
13. Xaltuxtashevich M. K. Libraries are the cradle of culture. – 2022.
14. Omonturdiev O. realization of youth interests in democratic reform (on the example of Uzbekistan) //American Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Sciences. – 2023. – T. 11. – C. 46-49.